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Formulation of protein-loaded nanoparticles via Freeze-Drying

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ABSTRACT

Several nanotechnology-based formulation strategies have been reported for the oral administration of biological drugs. However, a prerequisite often overlooked in developing these formulations is their adaptation to a solid dosage form. This work aimed to integrate a freeze-drying step in the formation of new insulin-zinc nanocomplexes, using mannitol or sucrose laurate (SLAE) as cryoprotective ingredients. The resulting freeze-dried insulin-zinc nanocomplexes exhibited physicochemical properties consistent with the target product profile, including a particle size of ~ 100 nm, a zeta potential close to neutrality (~ -15 mV) and a high association efficiency (> 90%). Importantly, integrating the freeze-drying step in the formulation significantly improved the colloidal stability of the system and preserved the stability of the insulin molecules. Results from *in vitro* and *in vivo studies* indicated that the insulin activity remained fully retained throughout the entire formulation and freeze-drying processes. Overall, the results highlighted the utility of freeze-drying as a critical step in the development of insulin-zinc nanocomplexes -for oral administration.

Keywords

Peptide/protein delivery, freeze-drying, oral administration, intestinal absorption, nanocomplexes, nanostructures

INTRODUCTION

Peptide/protein drug therapeutics represent a powerful strategy for treating a variety of diseases nowadays, owing to their high specificity and potency in comparison to small molecule drugs [1]. However, their structural complexity, makes them vulnerable and limits their capacity to overcome biological barriers and reach their targets [1,2]. Fortunately, drug delivery technologies are providing specific solutions for their administration through routes other than parenteral injection, particularly in the field of oral administration, which is fundamental for chronic treatments [1,3]. Notably, nanocarriers such as polymeric nanoparticles [4,5], lipid nanocarriers [6,7], nanocomplexes [8,9], micelles [10,11] and polymer-lipid nanocapsules (NCs) [12,13] stand out.

In the development of oral protein nanoformulations there are critical aspects that have been underestimated in the scientific literature. These include (i) the acceptability of the presentation for the intended modality of administration; for the oral route, the preferred format is a solid dosage form; and (ii) the necessity to have adequate storage stability over extended periods of time [14,15]. In this context, freeze-drying is by far the most commonly used process in the pharmaceutical field to convert solutions or suspensions into a powdered product [15–17].

An important aspect in the development of freeze-dried formulations is related to the use of a high concentration of cryoprotective agents (2%-30% w/v) [15,17,18], which may affect their performance. Despite of this, the assessment of a nanoparticles freeze-drying process has simply relied on the analysis of the particle size after reconstitution [19–21], while the overall performance of the system was assumed to be maintained. Only a few works have evaluated key parameters of protein-loaded nanoparticles [22–25] upon freeze-drying [22], and only one, to the best of our knowledge, evaluated the performance *in vivo* as well [23].

In addition to preserving the critical quality attributes of nanoformulations, it is essential to achieve a very high protein loading due to the dilution process during freeze-drying. However, the limited protein loading capacity of the majority of nanocarriers [24] compromises their potential use in the form of a dried oral dosage form [25]. In the light of this scenario, our approach towards the development of oral protein dried formulations has been adopted from a different perspective, involving the integration of the freeze-drying process as a step in the production of protein-loaded nanoformulations. Building upon the principle of forming insulin-Zn nanocomplexes, developed by our group, we explored a new formulation strategy that entails the integration of a freeze-drying step and the incorporation of sucrose lauric acid ester (SLAE) [26,27], a permeation enhancer, and compare its behavior with that of a classical cryoprotectant such as mannitol [15,28]. The developed formulations were evaluated for their final physicochemical properties and performance *in vitro*, as well as their capability to preserve protein bioactivity *in vitro* and *in vivo*, specifically assessing their oral efficacy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS

Recombinant human insulin hexamer Insuman[®] (Mw 5808 Da) was generously provided by Sanofi (Paris, France). Pharmaceutical grade Zn acetate dehydrate (EMPROVE[®]) was obtained

from Merck Millipore, Germany. HCl and NaOH solutions, acetic acid and trifluoroacetic acid were purchased from Scharlau (Barcelona, Spain). Lauric Acid Ester (SLAE, Surfhope SF) was obtained from Mitsubishi Kagaku (Dusseldorf, Germany). D-Mannitol (pharma quality) was purchased from Acofarma (Madrid, Spain). Sodium perchlorate monohydrate and pancreatin from porcine pancreas (4 USP) were acquired from Sigma-Aldrich (Madrid, Spain). Physiological serum (NaCl 0.9% w/v) was purchased from Braun (Hessen, Germany). Ultrapurified water was obtained from Millipore Milli-Q Plus water purification system (Darmstadt, Germany). All other chemicals were of analytical grade.

The HepG2 cell line was obtained from ECACC (UK, distributed by SIGMA) and cultured in growth medium: EMEM (1 g glucose/L, SIGMA, UK) supplemented with 10 % FBS (GIBCO, Thermo South America), 1% Non-essential aminoacids (GIBCO, Thermo Grand Island USA), 2 mM L-Glutamine (SIGMA Brazil), 1% Penicillin-Streptomycin (SIGMA Israel). Cells were passaged once per week by trypsinization (10x Trypsin solution, SIGMA USA) for 5 minutes and passaged through a 18-gauge needle to obtain a single cell suspension. They were used between passages 3 to 20. Viafect was obtained from Promega (Madison USA), Turbofect was purchased from Thermo (Lithuania), pMAXGFP was acquired from Lonza (Köln Germany), pSynSRE-T-luc and pSynSRE-Mut-T-luc were obtained from Addgene (Cambridge USA). Hoescht 33258 and Type I collagen solution in PBS were obtained from (SIGMA Israel).

Male Sprague–Dawley rats (250–300 g) were obtained from the Central Animal House, University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain). They were kept under 12 h light/12 h dark cycles and fed a standard laboratory rodent diet (Panlab A04, Panlab laboratories). All animal experiments were reviewed and approved by the ethics committee of the University of Santiago de Compostela (ref. 1500AE/12/FUN01/FIS02/ CDG3) according to the European and Spanish regulations for the use of animals in animal studies; performed therefore in compliance with the Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and Council.

METHODS

Preparation of freeze-dried protein-loaded formulations

Firstly, insulin-Zn nanocomplexes were obtained in a two-step procedure, consisting of inducing the interaction of insulin and Zn by pH adjustment followed by dispersion of the complex material in buffer media. For this purpose, a 1.5 mg/mL Insulin solution in 0.05N HCl was mixed with a 20 mg/mL Zn acetate aqueous solution at a 1:6 molar ratio, and its pH adjusted to 5.4 by addition of 0.1N NaOH under magnetic stirring at 300 rpm, inducing the co-precipitation of the components. Following, this mixture was incubated at 4°C [29] during 3h to allow for the crystallization of the protein-metal complex. After the incubation period, the complex material was allowed to reach room temperature (RT) for 4 minutes, re-suspended by vortexing (20s) and poured over PBS 10 mM under magnetic stirring at 300 rpm and 1:1 volume ratio during 30s, resulting in a colloidal suspension of nanocomplexes (with a final insulin concentration of 0.75 mg/mL). Subsequently, the nanocomplexes were subjected to freeze-drying in the presence of either mannitol or SLAE as cryoprotectant. Initially, a screening of cryoprotectant concentrations was carried out, from which the best performing concentrations of each

cryoprotectant were selected based on their ability to maintain the formulation properties after lyophilization while minimizing the amount of cryoprotectant required for incorporation. To this end, the nanocomplexes suspension was mixed with equal volumes of cryoprotectant solutions of increasing concentration under magnetic stirring (300 rpm) and immediately frozen by immersion in liquid nitrogen. The samples were kept at -80°C until freeze-drying, which was conducted in a Genesis VirTis 25EL pilot lyophilizer. The primary drying was performed at -40°C for 43 h (200 mTorr), followed by secondary drying at 20°C (3 h at the same vacuum). The resulting powder product was stored at RT in a desiccator. For reconstitution, ultrapure water was added to the freeze-dried product in a volume corresponding to the initial nanocomplex concentration before mixing with the cryoprotector, followed by 30s of vortexing. The reconstituted nanocomplexes were subsequently evaluated *in vitro* and *in vivo*.

Physicochemical and morphological characterization

Particle size distribution and PDI were determined by dynamic light scattering (DLS) and zeta potential was determined from the electrophoretic mobility values by laser Doppler anemometry (LDA), in a Malvern Zetasizer equipment (NanoZS ZEN 3600, Malvern Instruments, Worcestershire, UK), equipped with a red laser light beam ($\lambda = 632.8$ nm). The formulation was directly measured without dilution at 25°C both before mixing with cryoprotectants and after reconstitution of the dry powder, with at least three different batches and triplicate analysis of each batch. In the case of mixtures containing SLAE and reconstituted lyophilizates, the average size and PDI result was significantly influenced by the appearance of a micelles peak around 10 nm, leading to a multimodal distribution. Therefore a distribution analysis was employed instead of cumulants analysis by monitoring, the major size intensity peak (Peak 1) to assess particle size (<https://www.malvernpanalytical.com/en/learn/knowledge-center/user-manuals/MAN0485EN.html>). The morphological evaluation of the formulation was carried out using a transmission electron microscope (TEM, CM12, Philips, Netherlands). For this, samples were placed on copper grids and stained with phosphotungstic acid (2% w/v in 500 mM buffer acetate pH 5.5, to prevent nanocomplex dissociation at acid pH) for 2 minutes and allowed to dry overnight in a desiccator.

Insulin association efficiency and loading capacity

The association efficiency (AE) of insulin to the nanocomplexes was analyzed by separating the nanocomplexes from their suspending aqueous medium followed, by direct and indirect analysis. For this purpose, 1 mL of formulation was subjected to ultracentrifugation (Beckman Coulter, Optima L-90K, Brea, USA, rotor 70.1Ti) at 70,000 rpm (average RCF 336,140 g) for 3h at 15°C, resulting in the separation of a nanocomplexes sediment from the suspending medium. After separating the supernatant, the pellet was dissolved in 0.1% v/v TFA, leading to the dissociation of Insulin-Zn complexation due to acidification [30]. Aliquots from both the supernatant (indirect quantification) and the TFA-dissolved pellet (direct quantification) were analyzed by HPLC using a reverse phase isocratic method as described elsewhere [13,31] (Agilent model, 1100 series LC with diode-array detector set at 214 nm, Santa Clara, USA) with a C18 column (Superspher® RP-18 endcapped) as stationary phase. The mobile phase was eluted at 1 mL/minute and consisted

of a 44:56 v/v mixture of a phase A (93:7 v/v phosphate buffer (0.1M, pH2.3) – acetonitrile) and a phase B (43:57 v/v phosphate buffer – acetonitrile). The AE (%) was calculated according to the equation:

$$AE(\%) = \frac{\text{Amount of insulin in isolated nanocomplexes}}{\text{Total insulin}} \times 100$$

The final insulin loading (LC% w/w) was calculated by dividing the amount of insulin associated (AE x Total Insulin in the formulation) by the total weight of nanocomplexes. For the quantification of insulin payload (%wt) in the freeze-dried product, a known amount of product was weighted in a precision balance (Kern, model ABT 120-5DM, Kern & Sohn, Balingen, Germany), dissolved in TFA 0.1% v/v and analyzed by HPLC.

Colloidal stability of the nanocomplexes in bio-relevant media

The colloidal stability of the nanocarriers in simulated intestinal fluid (SIF) was evaluated by analysis of particle size and PDI by DLS, while particle concentration in the sample was monitored by light intensity count rate [13,31,32]. SIF media (pH 6.8) was prepared following the procedures outlined in the pharmacopeia. The nanocomplex formulation was diluted to the concentration expected to be achieved in *in vivo* studies, taking into account animal physiology [33] and a target dose of 50 IU/Kg in rodents. Accordingly, 100 µL of the nanocomplex suspension was diluted in 400 µL of SIF and maintained in an incubator at 37°C (Heidolph Instruments GmbH & Co. KG, Schwabach, Germany) with a horizontal shaking speed of 300 rpm. At specified time points (0h, 0.5h, 1h, 2h and 4h), samples were directly measured using a Malvern Zetasizer equipment (NanoZS ZEN 3600, Malvern Instruments, Worcestershire, UK) (Attenuator 10). Each analysis was performed in triplicate using at least three different batches. Assessment of the colloidal stability of the formulation in enzyme-supplemented media as well as in other complex biorelevant media (e.g., FaSSIF-V2, FeSSIF-V2) was unfeasible due to the significant signal interference of complex media components, mainly enzyme and/or surfactants, with the formulation during measurement in the Zetasizer equipment.

***In vitro* insulin release profile**

Insulin release profiles from the nanocarriers were evaluated by incubating them in SIF media at 37°C with horizontal shaking (300 rpm, Heidolph Instruments GmbH & Co. KG, Schwabach, Germany). The dilution rate followed the aforementioned protocol to achieve the expected final insulin concentration *in vivo*. For this purpose, 200-µL aliquots were diluted with 800 µL of SIF and maintained in an incubator. After 0h, 0.5h, 1h, 2h and 4h, the samples were subjected to ultracentrifugation (Beckman Coulter, Optima L-90K, Brea, USA, rotor 70.1Ti, 70,000 rpm (average RCF 336,140 g) for 3h at 15°C. The resulting supernatants were withdrawn, and the corresponding pellets were dissolved in 0.1% v/v TFA. Both the released insulin (from the supernatants) and the insulin remaining associated with the nanocarriers (in the pellets) at each time point were analyzed by HPLC as described in the preceding sections.

***In vitro* protection against enzymatic degradation**

The capacity of the nanocarriers to protect the associated insulin against enzymatic degradation was evaluated by quantifying the amount of undegraded insulin remaining after incubating the formulation with 1% w/v pancreatin (4 USP)-supplemented SIF (SIF-p). To achieve this, and prior to the study, several dilutions of SIF-p and insulin solution in nanocarrier suspending media were mixed and incubated for 20 minutes at 37°C, with a horizontal shaking speed of 300 rpm). The reaction was then stopped by adding 0.1N HCl and placing the mixture on ice. Subsequently, the undegraded insulin was analyzed by HPLC (as described in section 2.1.3). The pancreatin:insulin ratio, resulting in a $t_{1/2}$ of approximately 20 minutes for the protein, was selected for the proteolysis study. For the proteolysis evaluation, 250 μ L of either nanocarrier suspension, insulin solution at the same concentration and same dispersing media as the control, or only dispersing media (as the pancreatin negative control), were mixed with SIF-p following the previously selected pancreatin:insulin ratio. The mixture was then incubated at 37°C with 300 rpm horizontal shaking (Heidolph Instruments GmbH & Co. KG, Schwabach, Germany). At predetermined intervals (0; 0.5; 1 and 2 h), the enzyme activity was terminated by adding 300 μ L of 0.1M HCl to each aliquot, which also induced the disruption of nanocomplexes due to nanocomplex dissociation at an acidic pH. The mixture was then placed on ice, and the remaining amount of insulin was analyzed by HPLC as previously described.

Cell-based insulin bioactivity assay

The insulin bioactivity of the freeze-dried product was tested in cells along, with fresh insulin as a positive control. To conduct this assessment, HepG2 cells derived from a human liver carcinoma, recognized as an insulin target organ, and known to be enriched in Insulin Receptor expression (<https://www.proteinatlas.org/ENSG00000171105-INSR/cell>), were selected for this study.

For the transfection process, the efficiency of Viafect and Turbofect was compared by measuring the transfection efficiency of a commercial plasmid preparation of pMAXGFP, following the standard recommended protocols. The efficiency was calculated measuring the number of GFP fluorescent cells in relation to the total number of cells stained with Hoescht 33258. Apoptosis, as indicated by condensed Hoescht-positive cells, was also measured and excluded from the efficiency calculation. Given that Viafect resulted in over 95% efficiency, while Turbofect yielded approximately 65%, all subsequent experiments were conducted using Viafect.

MW48 plates (Costar, Thermo NY USA) were pre-coated with a 100 μ g/ml solution of Type I collagen in PBS (stock solution: 4mg/ml) and subsequently washed three times with PBS. For each assay, 24,000 HepG2 cells were seeded per well in growth medium (EMEM, supplemented with 10 % FBS, 1% Non-essential aminoacids, 2 mM L-Glutamine, and 1% Penicillin-Streptomycin) and allowed to proliferate for a full day. The following day, a transfection mix composed of DNA plasmids (85 ng of promoter + 35 ng of empty RSV plasmid per well), Viafect transfection reagent (1.5 μ L per well) and EMEM (23.5 μ L per well) was prepared for all wells combined and incubated for 20 minutes. The plasmids used were pSynSRE-T-luc, containing the -324 to -225 bp fragment of the hamster HMG-CoA synthase promoter, which included the SRE elements upstream of the minimal HMG-CoA synthase TATA box (-28 to +39), and pSynSRE-Mut-T-luc, which carried four point mutations in SRE elements of the promoter. Previous studies

have demonstrated that Insulin regulates HMG-CoA synthase expression via these SRE sites in human cells, and this effect is nullified in the mutated promoter [34]. Simultaneously, the cell medium was replaced with growth medium containing 2 mM metformin, to reduce basal luciferase expression while the cells were undergoing transfection. Subsequently, 25 μ L of the transfection mix was added per well and incubated for 6 h. Following this, three washes with warm PBS were performed, and the cells were switched to a deprived medium (growth medium containing only 0.5% v/v FBS), supplemented with either an insulin control solution or insulin extracted from the reconstituted freeze-dried nanocomplexes. Insulin extraction was achieved by acidification of the reconstituted nanocomplexes to induce dissociation (pH 3.5), which was then further diluted in PBS (pH 7.2) to a final concentration of 4 IU/mL, creating non-harmful conditions for cell culture. Samples were added to cell wells at concentrations ranging from 50 to 500 microIU/ml or an equivalent vehicle volume. Each condition was tested in six-to-eight replicates. After 20 h, the wells were washed three times with PBS, after which 40 μ L of PassiveLysis Buffer was added to each well and incubated for 20 minutes. The lysates were collected and frozen at -20^o C. Luciferase activity was assessed as described elsewhere [32,35] using 15 μ L of lysate in a Mithras microplate reader (LB940, Berthold, Bad Wildbad Germany). The experiments were repeated three times. Statistics and figures were processed with GraphPad 7. Initially, a Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test was applied. Subsequently, given the normal distribution, an unpaired t-test was employed to evaluate significance. Insulin –Vehicle concentrations were presented in parallel graphics, comparing the wild-type SynSRE-T-luc promoter with the mutated SynSRE-Mut-T-luc promoter.

***In vivo* studies in normoglycemic rats: insulin activity and formulation hypoglycemic efficacy**

Male Sprague–Dawley rats (250–300 g) were sourced from the Central Animal House, University of Santiago de Compostela, Spain. They were housed under 12 h light/12 h dark cycles and provided with a standard laboratory rodent diet (Panlab A04, Panlab laboratories). All animal experiments were reviewed and approved by the ethics committee of the University of Santiago de Compostela (ref. 1500AE/12/FUN01/FIS02/ CDG3) in accordance with the European and Spanish regulations for the use of animals in research studies, performed in compliance with the Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and Council.

In addition to cell-based assessments of insulin bioactivity preservation, the pharmacological effect of freeze-dried and reconstituted formulations was evaluated by subcutaneous (s.c.) administration to rats, in comparison with free insulin [13]. For this purpose, the rats were fasted for 4h before the study, with free access to water. A solution containing free insulin and the previously freeze-dried, reconstituted formulation was administered at a dose of 1 IU/Kg. Before administration (0h), blood samples were collected from the tail vein, and initial blood glucose levels were measured using a hand-held glucometer (Glucocard™ G+meter, Arkray Factory, Japan), with subsequent monitoring every hour.

For the pharmacological evaluation of the formulation, rats underwent surgical implantation of an intestinal catheter, with the proximal end of the cannula tunneled subcutaneously to exit at

the back of the neck, and sutured [13,31]. The animals were allowed to recover for 6 days and were monitored for general well-being, with their weights recorded daily. Prior to administration, the animals were fasted for 4h, with free access to water. Before administration (0h), blood samples were drawn from the tail vein, and initial blood glucose levels were measured with a hand-held glucometer (Glucocard™ G+meter, Arkray Factory, Japan). Only animals with initial glucose level over 70 mg/dL were included in the study. Subsequently, either the formulation or a free insulin solution in the same dispersion medium was administered via intestinal injections at a dose of 50 IU/Kg (n = 6). Prior to administration (0h), blood samples were drawn from the tail vein, and initial blood glucose levels were measured with a hand-held glucometer (Glucocard™ G+meter, Arkray Factory, Japan), with subsequent monitoring every hour.

Statistics

All experiments were conducted in triplicate and the results were presented as mean ± standard deviation (SD). Statistical analysis was carried out by first applying a Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test. For data that were normally distributed, statistical significance was determined by one way ANOVA with a Fisher's LSD test (GraphPadPrism, GraphPad software Inc., CA, USA). All other analyses were performed using a Student's t- test. The level of significance was set at probabilities of *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001 and **** p < 0.0001.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Production and characterization of freeze-dried of insulin-zinc nanocomplexes

The primary objective of this study was to design a new manufacturing process for insulin-zinc nanocomplexes, involving a stabilizing freeze-drying step. It is important to note that the freeze-drying process was not solely aimed at stabilizing a pre-existing nanoformulation but was also intended to enable the incorporation of stabilizing agents into the nanostructure. To our knowledge, only a limited number of studies have explored the applicability of a lyophilization process in the creation of drug-loaded nanocarriers. For instance, our laboratory previously introduced this approach for enhancing the association of amikacin sulphate, a highly polar drug, to poly(alkylcyanoacrylate) nanoparticles [36]. Subsequently, a small number of studies mentioned the use of freeze-drying for the production of nanocrystals [37–39] and lipid nanoparticles [40]. In this current research, we developed an oral insulin formulation containing Zn²⁺ as a complexing agent, and SLAE or mannitol as stabilizing agents for the freeze-drying process. As previously indicated, SLAE was chosen for its permeation-enhancing properties [26,27], while mannitol was employed for comparative purposes due to its widespread use as cryoprotectant [15,28], and also because it serves as a non-glycemic alternative to other commonly used cryoprotectants such as trehalose [41].

Insulin-Zn coated nanocomplexes produced by freeze-drying displayed a size of approximately 100 nm, a 0.3 PDI, and a low negative zeta potential (-16.7 ± 1.5) (**Table 1**). These nanocomplexes demonstrated an exceptionally high protein loading (90%) as well as a high protein association efficiency (90%) (**Table 1**).

Cryoprotectant	Formulation state	Size (nm)	PDI	ZP (mV)	Initial loading (%)	Loading efficiency (%)
None	Before freeze-drying	101 ± 11	0.3	-16.7 ± 1.5	92.6	91.2 ± 3.7
Mannitol	Before freeze-drying	98 ± 11	0.4	-	-	-
Mannitol	After freeze-drying	130 ± 1	0.3	-14.5 ± 2.6	1.5*	76.2 ± 4.8
SLAE	Before freeze-drying	153 ± 20	-	-	-	-
SLAE	After freeze-drying	213 ± 17	-	-16.4 ± 1.5	1.8*	78.7 ± 5.8

Table 1 Physicochemical parameters of formulations before and after addition of cryoprotectants, before and after freeze-drying and subsequent reconstitution. (*) loading values considering the amount of surfactant included in the formulation. (mean ± SEM, n = 6)

TEM imaging revealed that the nanoformulation had an orthogonal shape and a very small size (< 50 nm), which was smaller than the one obtained from DLS characterization (**Fig. 1A**). This discrepancy was attributed to the limitations of DLS in measuring non-spherical structures [42]. Despite these positive aspects, this formulation exhibited instability upon incubation in biorelevant fluids (Simulated Intestinal Fluid, SIF) (**Fig. 2A**). Consequently, in an effort to enhance the stability of the nanoformulation, we introduced a freeze-drying process involving the use of functional excipients. Additionally, the resulting powder was anticipated to be suitable for the development of a solid dosage form.

Fig. 1 TEM images of A) freshly prepared nanocomplexes; B) mannitol-containing freeze-dried and re-suspended nanocomplexes; C) SLAE-containing freeze-dried and re-suspended nanocomplexes

Fig. 2 Colloidal stability in SIF of (A) freshly prepared nanocomplexes; (B) mannitol-containing freeze-dried and re-suspended nanocomplexes; (C) SLAE-containing freeze-dried and re-suspended nanocomplexes, (mean \pm SD, n = 3)

Mannitol was chosen as a conventional cryo- and lyoprotectant [28], known for its bulking, stabilizing, and tonicity adjusting properties [18,43]. Initially, a screening of various mannitol concentrations was conducted to determine the minimum amount of cryoprotectant required to maintain particle size following the reconstitution of the freeze-dried powder (**Fig. 3A**). Based on this screening, a concentration of 2.5% w/v of mannitol was selected (**Table 1**)

Fig. 3 Size and PDI values of nanocomplexes freeze-dried after the addition of increasing concentrations of (A) mannitol and (B) SLAE (mean \pm SD, n = 3)

On the other hand, SLAE was incorporated as a crucial component in the formulation. SLAE is a non-ionic surfactant with the capacity to temporarily alter the integrity of the membrane barrier by fluidizing and extracting intercellular lipids [26,27,44,45]. Therefore, it was deemed highly promising for enhancing the transport of insulin molecules across the intestinal epithelium. Besides its surfactant properties, SLAE is also considered a GRAS (Generally Recognized as Safe) excipient and a potential cryoprotectant due to its stabilizing properties [18,46]. The experimental conditions and results are illustrated in **Fig. 3B**. Some technological obstacles were encountered during size measurement due to the formation of SLAE micelles [47] mixed with the nanocomplexes (**Fig. 1S**). To address this issue, the peak of size intensity attributed to the nanocomplexes was monitored before and after freeze-drying (**Fig. 3B**, **Fig. S1**). Based on this assessment, a concentration of 2.0% w/v SLAE was chosen as it allowed for the maintenance of a similar DLS intensity distribution before and after lyophilization (**Fig. 1S**). Moreover, TEM examination of the reconstituted powder revealed structures of identical size and shape compared to fresh and mannitol freeze-dried formulations (**Fig. 1C**). The size value obtained for the nanocomplexes via DLS, based on the major intensity peak, was moderately increased relative to the original formulation following the addition of SLAE and freeze-drying (**Table 1**). Thus, a concentration of 2.0% w/v SLAE was ultimately deemed successful for the development of the freeze-dried formulation.

In vitro characterization of the freeze-dried formulations upon incubation in bio-relevant fluid: colloidal stability, insulin release and protection against enzymatic degradation

Initially, the colloidal stability of the freeze-dried formulations and their subsequent reconstitution in SIF was assayed. In contrast to the non-freeze-dried insulin-Zn nanocomplexes (**Fig. 2A and S2**), these freeze-dried formulations exhibited stability in terms of both size and count rate. This stabilizing effect was attributed to the formation of a protective layer of the cryoprotectant on the surface of the nanocomplexes. The water replacement hypothesis posits that lyoprotectants act as substitutes for water by forming hydrogen bonds with the polar

groups on the surface of nanoparticles [48–50]. Moreover, an alternative potential explanation for this stabilization effect could be related to the drying process, which possibly resulted in a more compact interaction of insulin and zinc molecules. Overall, the freeze-drying step in the presence of either mannitol or SLAE was shown to be an effective strategy to provide the nanocomplexes with colloidal stability in the biorelevant fluid of interest.

The results of the *in vitro* insulin release studies conducted in SIF for the formulation are presented in **Figure 4**. To ensure the accuracy of the released insulin values, we also analyzed the amount of insulin in the pellet obtained from each sample (non-released insulin). The total amount of insulin recovered from each sample (total insulin analyzed, i.e. the sum of released and non-released insulin) was close to 100% in all cases, confirming the consistency between the values of released and non-released insulin (**Fig. 4**). Both formulations, incorporating mannitol or SLAE, exhibited a similar profile characterized by a small burst of release (15-30%) followed by a negligible release thereafter. While a burst release is typical of protein-loaded nanocarriers [24], the absence of a significant release at later time points was unexpected. In this context, the high centrifugal force and prolonged duration of ultracentrifugation employed in the study, along with potential interactions of the released protein with other components dissociated from the formulation, may have facilitated the precipitation of the protein upon its release.

Fig. 4 Cumulative protein release profile in SIF (A) mannitol-containing freeze-dried and re-suspended nanocomplexes; (B) SLAE-containing freeze-dried and re-suspended nanocomplexes (mean \pm SD, n = 3)

Subsequently, the ability of the freeze-dried formulations to protect insulin from degradation was examined in a proteolysis study [9,51]. **Fig. 5** illustrates the percentage of non-degraded insulin remaining after incubation in pancreatin-supplemented medium at predetermined time points. A solution of free insulin was used as reference, which demonstrated a reduction in the amount of non-degraded protein from the very initial stage of the assay, and complete degradation after 4h of incubation. In contrast, both the mannitol and SLAE formulations exhibited higher values of remaining insulin up to 2h, suggesting that these formulations effectively slowed down the degradation rate of the protein (**Fig. 5**). This protective effect could be attributed to the enzymatic inhibitory properties of zinc [52] and to the reduced accessibility of the protein associated with the zinc molecules to the enzymes. In addition, the observation

that higher relative amounts of insulin were degraded compared to the corresponding relative amounts of peptide released at the same time points (**Fig. 5** and **Fig. 4**) is in accordance with the hypothesis that the low values of release obtained may be attributed to the isolation procedure and/or interactions with components released from the formulation.

Fig. 5 Percentage of insulin that remains non-degraded upon incubation in pancreatin-supplemented SIF. The graphic shows the values obtained from the incubation of a free insulin in solution vs. insulin from freeze-dried and re-suspended nanocomplexes using mannitol or SLAE as cryoprotectant vs. free insulin (mean \pm SD, n = 3)

In vitro cell-based bioactivity study of insulin

For cell-based bioactivity studies, Hep G2 cells transfected pSynSRE-T-luc-, expressing luciferase activity over a transfection control promoter (beta-galactosidase) in response to insulin, were utilized [32]. Similarly, pSynSRE-Mut-T-luc-transfected cells, bearing four-point mutations in the insulin-responsive element and therefore not responsive to the presence of insulin in terms of luciferase activity, served as the negative control. Fresh solutions of free insulin at various concentrations were used as the as positive control, inducing a dose-response luciferase activity in pSynSRE-T-luc transfected cells, while no statistically significant effect was observed in pSynSRE-Mut-T-luc transfected cells, thus validating the assay (**Fig. 6A**). Furthermore, insulin from both, the mannitol and SLAE freeze-dried formulations, when incubated at different concentrations, elicited luciferase expression at significantly distinct levels from the control (**Fig. 6B and 6C**), confirming the bioactivity of the extracted insulin. Notably, the signal obtained for the SLAE-containing formulation exhibited a moderately higher signal than that of the mannitol-containing formulation at equivalent concentrations (**Fig. 6B and 6C**). This difference could be attributed to the potential permeation enhancer properties of SLAE [27,44,45], which may have facilitated higher cellular uptake. Overall, the results confirmed the bioactivity of insulin after processing into a formulation and the freeze-drying process [32,51].

Fig. 6 Cell-based insulin bioactivity values measured as a function of luciferase activity in pSynSRE-T-luc-transfected cells over a transfection control promoter (beta-galactosidase); (A) reference values of luciferase activity of fresh insulin solutions, showing a dose-response luciferase activity in pSynSRE-T-luc-transfected cells and no statistically significant effect observed in pSynSRE-Mut-T-luc-transfected cells (negative control); (B) insulin bioactivity from the reconstituted SLAE formulation as a function of luciferase activity; (C) insulin bioactivity from the reconstituted mannitol formulation as a function of luciferase activity. The results are presented as the means \pm SD, $n = 5$ independent experiments with 6–8 replicates per condition in each (significance levels compared to the control * $p \leq 0.05$; *** $p \leq 0.001$, **** $p \leq 0.001$)

***In vivo* studies in normoglycemic rats: insulin bioactivity and formulation hypoglycemic efficacy**

Finally, the bioactivity of the SLAE formulation was evaluated *in vivo* in normoglycemic rats by administering a s.c. injection of 1 UI/Kg dose of either free insulin as positive control or reconstituted freeze-dried formulation. As shown in **Fig. 7** and **Table 2**, the SLAE containing freeze-dried formulation led to a decrease in blood glucose down to 63% over the initial values within the first 30 minutes, which rapidly returned to the initial values. In contrast, free insulin prompted a more pronounced response, resulting in a significantly lower blood glucose at 1h (72% vs. 34%) (**Fig. 7** and **Table 2**). It remains to be determined whether this distinct profile is due to a partial loss of protein bioactivity or a different absorption profile of insulin arising from its slow release from the injected nanocomplexes. Notably, the presence of zinc and its interaction with insulin is known to be responsible for the delayed dissolution of insulin crystals formed upon administration in initially marketed s.c. formulations [53].

Fig. 7 *In vivo* assessment of insulin bioactivity upon s.c. administration of SLAE formulation vs. free insulin to healthy rats, as a function of normalized blood glucose values (% of the initial blood glucose value) (mean \pm SEM, n = 6) (significance levels comparing values at the same time point * $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.01$)

Furthermore, the hypoglycemic response of the SLAE formulation was assessed in fully awake, normoglycemic rats through intrajejunal (i.j.) administration [31,32]. This animal model was chosen to avoid the variable glycemic responses commonly observed in the streptozotocin (STZ)-induced diabetic model [13,31]. However, it should be noted that this healthy model may potentially underestimate the effect of insulin due to the autoregulation phenomenon [31,32]. The results obtained following i.j. administration of the SLAE formulation indicated a modest yet sustained decrease in blood glucose levels of up to 32% over initial values, which was maintained for up to 24h (**Fig. 8** and **Table 2**). These findings are consistent with previously published results by our group and others in the same animal model [31,32,54,55] and led us to conclude that the developed dried formulation facilitated a certain absorption of insulin.

Fig. 8 *In vivo* assessment of the hypoglycemic efficacy upon i.j. administration of SLAE formulation vs. free insulin to healthy rats, as a function of normalized blood glucose values (% of the initial blood glucose value) (mean \pm SEM, n = 8) (significance levels comparing values at the same time point * $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.01$)

Formulations	Dose (IU/Kg)	C _{min}	T _{min} (h)	AAC	PA (%)
Insulin s.c.	1	29 ± 1	1.0	93	100
SLAE formulation s.c.	1	48 ± 2	0.5	137	-
Insulin i.j.	50	86 ± 4	24.0	145	2.1
SLAE formulation i.j.	50	69 ± 3	24.0	484	10.5

Table 2 Parameters of plasma glucose levels and relative pharmacological bioavailability of the SLAE formulation and insulin solution upon intrajejunal administration (i.j.) compared to subcutaneous administration (s.c.) (mean ± SEM, n = 6 for s.c. data, n = 8 for i.j. data). C_{min}: minimum plasma glucose concentration (% of initial); T_{min}: time to C_{min}; AAC area above the glucose level time curves; PA: relative pharmacological bioavailability, based on AAC for s.c. administration

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we introduced an innovative methodology for developing zinc-insulin nanoparticles in a dried form. The key of our innovation lies in a strategic application of freeze-drying, a process that played a crucial role for the interaction between the stabilizing agents and the nanoparticles. This approach not only preserved the activity of the associated protein but also enhanced the stability of the resulting freeze-dried nanoformulations. These stabilized formulations exhibited satisfactory performance in biologically relevant fluids, eliciting a substantial response upon in vivo administration. Moreover, the subsequent powdered products featured a high protein payload, positioning them as promising candidates for oral delivery. The results highlight the effectiveness of integrating a freeze-drying step as an essential component of nanocarrier design, enhancing its performance as a delivery system. This approach could serve as a pivotal asset to yield powdered dosage forms with increased drug loading and enhanced in vitro and in vivo stability, representing an innovative tool in the field of oral protein and peptide delivery systems.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no competing interests.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors contributed either to the study conception, design, or the analysis performed during this work. The first draft of the manuscript was written by Matilde Durán Lobato and María José Alonso, and all authors commented on previous versions of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The datasets generated during this work can be available on reasonable request.

ETHICS APPROVAL

All animal experiments were reviewed and approved by the ethics committee at the University of Santiago de Compostela ID: 1500AE/12/FUN01/FIS02/CDG3 (Spanish Royal Decree 1201/2005, of October 10th) and ID: 15010/17/17002 (Spanish Royal Decree 53/2013, of February 1st) and were executed in accordance with governing Spanish law and European Directives and Guidelines for the use of animals in animal studies; performed therefore in compliance with the Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and Council of 22nd September 2010 on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes and under the Spanish Royal Decree 53/2013 February 1st on the protection of animals used for experimental and other scientific purposes, including teaching.

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Fig S1 Size distribution by intensity results from DLS measurements of mixtures of the formulation in the presence of increasing SLAE concentrations before vs. after freeze-drying and powder reconstitution

Fig S2 Compiled results of size distribution by intensity obtained along the colloidal stability study in SIF (0h to 4h) with the formulation freeze-dried with SLAE